

Photocatalytic action of silver-titanium dioxide nanocomposite against pathogenic bacteria

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Abstract : Various waterborne disease outbreaks have been reported even after disinfection with conventional techniques due to development of resistance in microorganism. Moreover, generation of carcinogenic disinfection by-products (DBPs) poses additional problems. This has prompted an exploration of alternative antimicrobial agents for disinfection of water. Over the last few decades, photocatalysis has been widely applied for degradation of various pollutants and inactivation of waterborne microbial pathogens. The present study was focused on the synthesis and characterization of Ag-TiO₂ nanocomposite by doping of TiO₂ nanoparticles (NPs) with silver (Ag). Water disinfection studies were conducted in a photochemical reactor in batch mode using UV and visible light irradiated Ag-TiO₂ nanocomposite (NC). Studies conducted using four opportunistic bacterial pathogens, i.e. *Escherichia coli* (MTCC 443), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (RS1), *Burkholderia cepacia* (ES1) and *Acinetobacter baumannii* (RS4) revealed effective disinfection of 10³ CFU/mL of bacteria within 30 min even for visible light irradiated nanocomposite (5 mg/100 mL).

Keywords : Disinfection by-products, nanocomposite, pathogens, photocatalysis, water disinfection.

I. Introduction

Water disinfection is a crucial step for control of waterborne infectious diseases. Various conventional disinfection techniques, including chlorination and ozonation are associated with formation of carcinogenic disinfection-byproducts (DBPs)¹. Other disinfection approaches, such as, UV based disinfection is unable to provide residual disinfectant for long term effectiveness². Moreover, various microbial pathogens, such as, *Cryptosporidium* and *Giardia* are found difficult to inactivate effectively with conventional methods. These limitations have prompted research on alternative antimicrobial agents. Over the past few decades, photocatalysis using metal oxide nanoparticles and nanocomposites has been applied for degradation of various pollutants and inactivation of waterborne pathogens. Among these, TiO₂ is the most extensively used photocatalyst due to its

low cost, availability and effectiveness. Since TiO₂ is a semiconductor with a bandgap of 3.2 eV (anatase phase), UV irradiation (at $\lambda < 380$ nm) of TiO₂ excites electrons from the valence band to the conduction band, thereby generating electron hole (e⁻-h⁺) pairs. These electrons and holes further react with dissolved oxygen and water and subsequently, generates a series of reactive oxygen species (ROS), which are found to be responsible for oxidative degradation of organic pollutants and microbial inactivation²⁻⁵. However, a few limitations of TiO₂ based photocatalysis limits its widespread application. These include high probability of electron hole recombination and dependence on UV irradiation. Dependence on UV irradiation not only increases the overall cost of treatment, it also increases the risk of UV exposure during handling of the UV source. Moreover, disinfection using photocatalysis relying on ROS

generation for microbial inactivation is often reported to be a slower process as compared to chlorination and other conventional disinfection techniques³.

Although a few studies have explored the application of TiO₂ based photocatalysis for water disinfection, more work is needed on design of visible light activated photocatalysts. The present study focused on the synthesis of Ag-TiO₂ nanocomposite (NC) by doping TiO₂ photocatalyst with AgNPs in order to minimize the electron-hole recombination and reduce the bandgap so as to make the photocatalyst effective even under visible light irradiation. The antimicrobial activity of the nanocomposite synthesized was also tested using various opportunistic pathogenic bacteria.

II. Materials and methods

A. Reagents

Silver nitrate (AgNO₃, >99% pure), sodium borohydride (NaBH₄, >99% purity) and trisodium citrate (TSC) were purchased from Merck (India). Titanium(IV) isopropoxide (TIP) was procured from Sigma-Aldrich (USA). Other reagents, such as, methanol, ethanol, acetic acid, nitric acid, hydrochloric acid and sulfuric acid were obtained from Merck (Germany). Nutrient broth and bacteriological nutrient agar were procured from Hi Media (Mumbai, India). All reagents supplied were of analytical grade and were used as received.

B. Microbial samples and their preparation

Escherichia coli is considered to be an indicator organism of fecal contamination in drinking water⁶. Therefore, *E. coli* was initially used for evaluating the antimicrobial effectiveness of the synthesized nanocomposite. *E. coli* (MTCC 443) and *Burkholderia cepacia* (ES1, MTCC 5332) were procured from IMTECH (Chandigarh, India). *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (RS1, GeneBank accession No. KF751345) and *Acinetobacter baumannii* (RS4, KF751346) were isolated by previous researchers in our lab from hydrocarbon contaminated soil/sediment/

oily sludge⁷. These bacteria were grown by inoculating 100 µL of stock culture in 100 ml sterile nutrient broth and incubating overnight in a rotary shaker operated at 180 rpm and maintained at 37°C. At the end of log growth phase, the culture was centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 10 min and the pellet was washed thrice using sterile phosphate buffer (pH 7.2). Finally, the culture was sufficiently diluted using phosphate buffer to obtain an absorbance of unity at 600 nm. This suspension was subsequently diluted and used in the disinfection studies. During the disinfection studies the concentration of viable bacteria over a period of 1–2 h was determined using the standard plate count method.

C. Synthesis of silver titanium dioxide (Ag-TiO₂) nanocomposite

Ag-TiO₂ NCs were synthesized using a sol gel method⁸ with some modifications. Briefly, 4.5 ml of TIP was dissolved in 42 ml ethanol and kept under stirred condition. First deionized water (3.5 ml) and subsequently AgNO₃ (100 mg, after 1.5 h of adding water) were added to the mixture and stirring was continued. After 4 h of stirring, NaBH₄ (30 mg) was added drop-wise for reduction of Ag⁺ to Ag⁰. Subsequently, the solution was kept in an oven at 80°C for 12 h for drying. The dried powder was grinded and subsequently calcined in a muffle furnace at 500°C for 1 h. The Ag-TiO₂ nanocomposite prepared was characterized and used for the disinfection studies. TiO₂ NPs were prepared using the same procedure by excluding the AgNO₃ addition step.

D. Characterization of the Ag-TiO₂ nanocomposite

The synthesized AgNP-TiO₂ nanocomposite was characterized using FEG-TEM, FEG-SEM, XRD and FTIR. The morphology of Ag/TiO₂ nanocomposite was examined using a HR-TEM (FEI, Tecnai G2, F30) at an accelerating voltage of 300 kV. The TEM images were analyzed using the image analysis software, *Image J*, to determine the size range and particle size distribution of the Ag-TiO₂ nanocomposite (NC). Its crystal structure was determined by ana-

lyzing the selected area electron diffraction pattern (SAED) using HR-TEM. Field Emission Gun-Scanning Electron Microscopy (FEG-SEM 7600F, JEOL, Japan) was employed to characterize the morphology and EDS detector attached to the FEG-SEM instrument was used to analyze the chemical composition. X-Ray diffraction (XRD) pattern was recorded at a scan rate of 0.017° per 10.16 s on a powder X-ray diffractometer (PANalytical X'pert PRO, Netherlands) of $\text{Cu-K}\alpha$ wavelength ($\lambda = 1.54 \text{ \AA}$) to study the crystalline structure. The NC coated on a glass substrate was scanned over a 2θ range of $10\text{--}80^\circ$ at a scan speed of 0.017° per 10.16 s. FTIR spectroscopy (3000 Hyperion Microscope with Vertex 80 FTIR System, Bruker, Germany) was employed to analyze the chemical composition. The NC was mixed with KBr as mulling agent, dried and analyzed over the range of $4500\text{--}450 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in diffuse reflectance mode.

E. Antimicrobial testing of the nanocomposite

The antimicrobial performance of Ag-TiO₂ nanocomposite was tested by conducting disinfection experiments in a photocatalytic reactor (Fig. 1) in batch mode in the presence of UV light (125 W Low pressure UV Lamp with radiant flux of 42 W/in^2) as well as visible light provided using 3 W LED light (radiant flux 1.2 W/in^2).

Fig. 1. Schematic of experimental set-up of the photocatalytic reactor.

The antibacterial activity was tested using 5 mg/100 ml of Ag-TiO₂ nanocomposite in a photochemical reactor using 200 ml *E. coli* spiked water (10^3 CFU/ml). The samples collected at various time were tested for number concentration of viable microbes using the standard plate count technique. Similar experiments with 10^3 CFU/mL *E. coli* were also conducted in dark with no photocatalyst, dark with Ag-TiO₂ NC, UV irradiation with no photocatalyst, UV irradiation with TiO₂ NPs and visible irradiation with TiO₂ NPs. The disinfection studies with visible light irradiated Ag-TiO₂ NC were also performed using three other strains, i.e. *P. aeruginosa* (RS1), *B. cepacia* (ES1) and *A. baumannii* (RS4). All the disinfection studies were performed in duplicate and uncertainty was expressed as standard error (SE).

F. Model fitting and statistical analysis

Disinfection rate constant (k) of the selected strains were determined by linear regression of the disinfection profile using the Chick-Watson model⁹ as shown in eq. (1).

$$\frac{N}{N_0} = e^{-kt} \quad (1)$$

where, N_0 is the initial number of bacteria at $t = 0$ and N is the number of bacteria at time t . All the studies were conducted in duplicate and single factor analysis of variance (ANOVA) test was performed to determine the statistical significance of the difference in the values of disinfection rate constant for various strains.

III. Results and discussion

A. Synthesis and characterization of Ag-TiO₂ nanocomposite

Ag-TiO₂ nanocomposite was synthesized using sol gel method. Pure TiO₂ nanoparticles were completely white in color whereas the Ag-TiO₂ nanocomposite was brownish in color. The color change in the nanocomposite revealed adsorption of AgNPs on the surface of TiO₂ nanoparticles thus confirming synthesis of the nanocomposite.

The shape size and morphology of the nanocomposite was examined under transmission electron microscopy (Fig. 2). FEG-TEM micrographs revealed spherical shape of the Ag-TiO₂ NC where, the bigger spherical particles of 40–60 nm corresponded to TiO₂ NPs and the smaller particles of size 10–30 nm with high contrast corresponded to AgNPs. The SAED rings (Fig. 2b) demonstrated presence of the planes of (111), (200), (220) and (311), corresponding to face centered crystal (fcc) structure of AgNPs. The crystal structure was further characterized by XRD.

Fig. 2. (a) FEG-TEM image and (b) SAED pattern of Ag-TiO₂ NC.

The XRD spectra (Fig. 3a) was acquired to determine the crystal structure of the nanocomposite. XRD spectra revealed the presence of body-centered tetragonal crystal structure with a number of significant peaks at 2θ values of 25.35°, 37.01°, 37.84°, 48.14°, 53.97° and 68.81° corresponding to (101), (103), (004), (200), (105) and (215) planes of anatase phase and 38.64°, 44.84°, 64.67° and 76.40° corresponding to lattice planes (111), (200), (220) and (311) of the fcc crystal structure of AgNPs, respectively. These results were found consistent with those reported in the literature by other researchers¹⁰. The XRD spectra of Ag-TiO₂ nanocomposite showed peaks corresponding to AgNPs also. Thus, there was no adverse effect on crystallinity of nanoparticles in the nanocomposite.

The FTIR spectra of the Ag-TiO₂ nanocomposite was recorded between the ranges 4000–400 cm⁻¹ (Fig. 3). The peaks at ~440 cm⁻¹ and ~1000 cm⁻¹ de-

Fig. 3. (a) XRD spectra and (b) FTIR spectra of Ag-TiO₂ NC.

scribed the Ti-O-Ti bending and Ti-O-H stretching vibrations, respectively. However, the peaks between 1600–1700 cm⁻¹ is due to stretching vibration in O-H bond in water molecules¹¹.

The SEM micrograph of the Ag-TiO₂ nanocomposite is shown in the inset of Fig. 4. The micrograph revealed spherical shape of particles in the nanocomposite and illustrated minimal aggregation between particles. In the micrograph, the nanoparticles of larger size corresponded to TiO₂ nanoparticles whereas the nanoparticles with smaller size and higher contrast (associated with the nanoparticles of larger size) corresponded to silver nanoparticles. Further, semi-quantitative analysis of the Ag-TiO₂ nanocomposite was done using the energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) detector associated with FEG-SEM. It is reported that heavy elements with high atomic number, such as, silver ($Z = 47$) back scatter more strongly than lighter elements

having lower atomic number, such as, Ti ($Z = 22$) and O ($Z = 8$)¹². Thus, metallic Ag can be recognized by its high contrast as compared to other elements. The EDX spectra, (Fig. 4) clearly depicted the peaks corresponding to Ti, O and Ag.

Fig. 4. EDS spectra of Ag-TiO₂ nanocomposite.

The peaks in the EDS spectra at 2.65 and 2.98 keV correspond to the binding energies of Ag L₁ and Ag L_{α2}. The peaks at 0.529, 4.505 and 4.93 keV correspond to the binding energies of Ti L₁, Ti K_{α1} and Ti K_{β3}. The peak at 0.533 keV represents the binding energy of O K edge, thereby confirming the presence of both Ag and TiO₂ in the nanocomposite. These results confirmed the crystalline growth of nanocomposite with homogeneous and uniform spherical shape of nanoparticles in Ag-TiO₂ nanocomposite.

B. Antibacterial activity of Ag-TiO₂ nanocomposite

The antibacterial activity of the nanocomposite synthesized was tested in a photocatalytic reactor (Fig. 1) in batch mode using 5 mg Ag-TiO₂ photocatalyst (PC) per 100 ml contaminated water having 10³ CFU/ml of *E. coli* MTCC 443 under stirred condition. Various control studies for water disinfection were conducted using UV light alone (without photocatalyst), TiO₂ NPs with and without UV irradiation and Ag-TiO₂ NC in the dark (Fig. 5a). Control studies with TiO₂ NPs in the absence of UV light exhibited negligible reduction in bacterial concentration. Another control study using Ag-TiO₂ NC conducted

under dark condition also exhibited incomplete killing of microorganisms and demonstrated that only silver nanoparticle present in the Ag-TiO₂ nanocomposite was unable to cause 3 log bacterial inactivation and thus could not show complete killing (Fig. 5a). A complete killing i.e. 3 log reduction was achieved within 80 min with UV irradiation alone, within 60 min with TiO₂ NPs in presence of UV light and within 30 min with Ag-TiO₂ nanocomposite for all the strains under visible light irradiation (Fig. 5a-b). Thus, Ag-TiO₂ nanocomposite served as an effective antimicrobial agent that could achieve complete disinfection even in the absence of UV irradiation.

Fig. 5. Bactericidal effect of (a) TiO₂ NPs and Ag-TiO₂ NC in the dark and upon exposure to UV and visible irradiation on *E. coli* and (b) visible light irradiated Ag-TiO₂ on various bacterial pathogens.

An initial shoulder was observed in the disinfection profile. This may be due to insufficient formation of free radicals initially. However, doping TiO₂ with silver nanoparticles significantly enhanced the antimicrobial efficacy of the nanocomposite. This could be due to synergistic effect of antimicrobial properties of TiO₂ and AgNPs. Membrane damage by reactive oxygen species (ROS) and subsequent penetration of nanoparticles inside the cell may have been responsible for inactivation. Penetration of nanoparticles inside bacterial cells may initiate a series of biochemical reactions including damage to structural integrity of proteins/enzymes, inhibition of DNA replication and ROS mediated degradation of cell contents¹³.

C. Mechanism of photocatalytic action of Ag-TiO₂ nanocomposite

The bandgap energy, i.e. the energy required to promote an electron from valence band (VB) to conduction band (CB) of anatase form of TiO₂ is approximately 3.2 eV. Due to the high bandgap, TiO₂ photocatalysis requires irradiation with high energy photons (with $\lambda < 385$ nm i.e. UV A light). Such high energy photons can provide sufficient energy to promote electrons (e⁻) from the valence band to the conduction band, thereby leaving a positively charged hole (h⁺) in the VB (eq. (2)). The electrons in the CB are free to migrate within the conduction band. The holes may be filled by migration of an electron from an adjacent molecule, thereby creating another hole, and so on. When these electrons and holes reach the surface, they react with other components through a series of reactions (illustrated in eqs. (2–8)) and give rise to formation of various reactive oxygen species (ROS) that adversely affect the microorganisms^{4,9}.

Since the holes are also mobile, there is high chance of electron-hole recombination, which reduces the efficiency of the process. Doping with metals or metallic nanoparticles is reported to reduce such recombination. Generally, a Schottky barrier is formed when materials with different work functions are combined. The excited electrons are transferred from the material with lower work function to the material with the higher work function until the two levels reach equilibrium to form a new Fermi energy level. The equilibrated Fermi level electrons under visible light irradiation are injected rapidly into the conduction band of the metal oxide via a surface plasmon resonance (SPR) phenomenon. These injected electrons are trapped by dissolved oxygen molecules in water to yield highly oxidative species, such as super-oxide radical anions (O₂^{-•}) and hydroxy radicals (•OH), which are responsible for microbial inactivation¹⁴. In this study, doping with Ag improved the overall disinfection efficiency thus, exhibiting synergistic photocatalytic activity. Silver ion mediated inactivation, ROS mediated inactivation and minimization of electron-hole recombination may have all contributed to the synergistic effect (Fig. 6). Improvement in charge separation may have occurred by the transfer of photogenerated electrons from Ag⁰ of AgNPs to the conduction band of TiO₂ thereby causing simultaneous formation of Ag^I, i.e. Ag⁺ ion. Researchers have also been demonstrated that Ag⁺ may be partially reduced to its original active state, i.e. Ag⁰ on light irradiation⁴. This interconversion between Ag⁰ and Ag^I may have a significant influence on inactivation performance of the irradiated nanocomposite.

D. Model fitting and disinfection kinetics

The Chick Watson model (eq. (1)) fit to disinfection kinetics of the various strains is shown in Fig. 5 and the rate constant values are listed in Table 1. The measured N₀ values were used and one param-

Fig. 6. Mechanism of inactivation of bacteria by Ag-TiO₂ NC.

eter fit was performed for determining the rate constant. Although the *R*² values were relatively high, visual observation reveals poor fit to data due to the initial shoulder zone observed.

Table 1. Disinfection rate constant (min⁻¹) for various strains

Microorganisms	MTCC 443	RS1	ES1	RS4
<i>k</i> (min ⁻¹)	0.191	0.221	0.224	0.210
SE	0.008	0.001	0.008	0.001
<i>R</i> ²	0.940	0.958	0.978	0.965

ANOVA analysis confirmed that the inactivation rate constant was affected by the bacterial strain

Fig. 7. Chick Watson model fit to disinfection kinetics for various strains inactivated using visible light irradiated Ag-TiO₂ NC.

(*p* < 0.05). Among all the strains, *B. cepacia* (ES1) exhibited the highest rate of inactivation, however, it was only marginally higher than that of the other strains.

IV. Conclusion

Ag-TiO₂ nanocomposite was successfully synthesized using a sol-gel method. The photocatalytic disinfection studies conducted using Ag-TiO₂ nanocomposite demonstrated effective inactivation of various bacterial pathogens in batch mode. Ag-TiO₂ nanocomposite present at a concentration of 5 mg/100 ml exhibited 3 log reduction within 30 min for all the bacterial pathogens in the presence of visible light. However, the same concentration of nanocomposite under dark condition caused inadequate inactivation. Thus, this nanocomposite has good potential for synergistic photochemical inactivation and the disinfection process based on visible light irradiated Ag-TiO₂ NC may be a cost-effective disinfection process for inactivating a broad spectrum of microorganisms.

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